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Between Violence and Non-Violence: Theories of Decolonization in the Israeli Settler-Colonial Project

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Abstract: In academic circles, Israel has been the subject of discussion relating to its resemblance to a settler colonial state. Tariq Dana in her article “Notes on the ‘Exceptionalism’ of the Israeli Settler-Colonial Project” argues the same, basing her argument on the workings of Zionism (166). Zionism is a settler colonialism project disguised as a movement, aims to reclaim a piece of land which was mythologically promised to the Jews. There have been attempts to decolonise the Palestinian land by building resistance forces which primarily use violence as means to achieve its goals. Franz Fanon in the chapter “On Violence” in his book “Wretched of the Earth” emphasises violence as a key element in the process of decolonization (35), however, Hanna Arendt in her work also titled “On Violence” discards violence as a medium to achieve any power. (155) She is of the opinion that violence reduces power and perpetuates further violence. This paper aims to critically examine both Fanon and Arendt's texts in the contexts of the ongoing Israel-Palestine conflict to determine whether violence or non-violence has been more successful in reaching the goal of decolonization for the Palestinian people. The work uses textual analysis of both texts and contextual reading of the condition of Palestine and its resistance towards Israel's settler colonial project and tries to arrive at a conclusion.

Keywords: Violence, Resistance, Settler-colonialism, decolonization, and Non-violence

Introduction

Violence has been a key element in the history of humankind. Hannah Arendt writes in her essay “On Violence” in the book *Crises of the Republic* that violence has played huge role in human affairs. (110) Different ages have utilised violence to achieve various goals. In the twentieth century, however, a lot of colonies started nationalist movements of liberation from

colonialism. These revolutions a lot of times were using violence, if we see in the case of India, there was a group labelled as “Garam Dal”, or in Kenya in Mau Mau Uprising. Violence began to play a huge role in decolonisation efforts across the globe.

In 1961, Frantz Fanon wrote the book “The Wretched of the Earth”, in this book the opening chapter is named “Concerning Violence”, Fanon studies violence in this chapter and explains its necessity in the process of colonisation. At the same time, many of the activists across the globe were choosing for a more moderate and non-violent ways of agitation and coercion. M. K Gandhi, Martin Luther King and Nelson Mandela chose the paths of non-violence and used it extensively in their process of revolution.

Eminent political philosopher Hannah Arendt, in her book “Crisis of the Republic” published in 1972, writes a chapter called “On Violence”. Arendt sheds light on how violence has been neglected throughout the history of humankind as a subject of study. She calls for the systemic study of violence which has been a major part of human life historically. She points out several important aspects of violence and its usage relating it to politics and power, these are later discussed in the essay. Where Fanon states the nature of decolonisation as a violent process, Hannah Arendt’s discredits violence as an entity capable of creating or withholding power.

In the view of both ideas formulated by the eminent theorists, this paper will analyse the various resistance movements commenced by the Palestinians and their successes and failures. The focus of this study will specifically be violence and its application in the process of resistance or colonisation of the Palestinian land. The study will undertake various historical movements and violent conflicts between Palestine and Israel and look it through the point of views of Frantz Fanon and Hannah Arendt.

Literature Review

Immanuel Wallerstein in his essay “Frantz Fanon: Reason and Violence” calls out the misinterpretation of Fanon’s ideas regarding violence and revolution. Wallerstein asks for a fresh look at his ideas. Wallerstein says that though Fanon said that violence is inherent in the process of decolonisation, he never advocated irrational violence. (223) Wallerstein also talk about the cathartic and cleansing feature of violence where it can help clear up the psyche of the native and help him in regaining his self-respect. (226)

Neil Roberts in his essay “Fanon, Sartre, Violence, and Freedom” presents several arguments relating to violence and freedom. Roberts says that there are two types of violence, intrinsic violence and instrumental violence. The intrinsic violence is a fundamental aspect of anti-colonial movement, the instrumental violence is inflicted with certain goals in mind such as monetary or political gain. He argues that Fanon’s idea of violence is the one of intrinsic and not instrumental. (146) Roberts also critiques the idea of non-violent

resistance, he takes up the example of Martin Luther King and MK Gandhi as contrary to that he picks up Malcolm X. Roberts quotes Malcolm “don't rule out the gun”. Roberts emphasises that Fanon is not endorsing violence, rather keeping the possibility open for violent struggles because in Fanon's view decolonisation itself is a violent process. (144)

K. Jha presents a critique of Fanon's idea of violence in his essay titled “Fanon's Theory Of Violence: A Critique”. Jha takes up two main points viz. The vague definition given by Fanon of violence. Jha contends that Fanon fails to clearly define the term violence and deal with it in the broadest manner possible. (160) The second point Jha raises is that violence cannot provide long-lasting solutions to problems, as suggested by Fanon. (164)

Hannah Arendt's idea of violence has been criticised by Chad Kautzer in his article “Political Violence and Race: A Critique of Hannah Arendt” where the author says that much of Arendt's contention with violence is relating to the violence of revolutionaries and decolonising movements while she systematically leaves out the state inflicted violence and racially targetted violence. (2) This point is specifically important in the context of this paper because on one side there is Palestinian resistance, on the other is a state which is inflicting violence.

Fanon on Violence

Frantz Fanon, a French Afro-Caribbean psychiatrist, philosopher and theorist. His is best known for his work on post-colonialism, racism, violence and liberty. Fanon is known as “the voice of the Third World.” (Wyrick 2) Fanon's work on decolonisation has brought him fame across the globe. Particularly, his work on violence has given birth to debates across academic circles. In his book, *The Wretched of the Earth*, Fanon writes a comprehensive chapter on violence and why it is a necessary element of any decolonisation movement. Fanon starts the chapter “Concerning Violence” with a declarative statement, saying “decolonisation is always a violent phenomenon.” (Fanon 3) Fanon gets this idea from the violent decolonising movements across the world. For example, “the Mau Mau Uprising in Kenya, the guerilla struggle in Portuguese colonies, and of course the Algerian Revolution.” (Wyrick 106)

Fanon does talk about violence, but his aim is not to justify violence but to study violence dialectically. Fanon want to show how violence is a necessity for the colonisers. To achieve this Fanon studies violence from three perspectives, the individual perspective, the national perspective and the international perspective. In “the individual perspective” Fanon talk about the effects of violence, inflicted by the coloniser, has on the colonised people.

Deborah Wyrick in her work *Fanon for Beginners* explains how material violence dehumanises and tortures the native people in order to keep them in the colonised position. Psychological violence forces the native to accept an inferior identity which has been give to

them by the coloniser. (107) When excessive violence is inflicted upon the native, Fanon says, it acts as a cleansing force. "At the level of individuals, violence is a cleansing force. It frees the native from his inferiority complex and from his despair and inaction; it makes him fearless and restores his self-respect." (Fanon 94)

Hannah Arendt on Violence

Hannah Arendt in the essay "On Violence" studies the complex relationship between violence, power and politics. Arendt writes in her essay about the negligence of violence as a subject of scrutiny. She contends that violence needs to be studied and brought into mainstream. (110) Speaking about the nature of violence, Arendt writes, that the violence has an instrumental nature, meaning that violence is a tool. Just like any other tool designed to help us in completing various tasks, violence also has specific function or purpose. (145) Arendt writes that way too often violence is equated with power and thus perceived as a legitimate means to achieve political goals. However, violence might destroy power, but it cannot create or withhold power. (155)

Arendt also criticises the philosophical idea that "good can emerge from evil". She suggests that such ideas can lead to justification for violence. According to her, violence is not a valid tool for political means, rather it undermines the very structure that seeks to establish. Talking about the long-lasting achievements of violence, Arendt writes that using violent means in political struggle may bring positive results, but that results are very short-lived and the "price is very high" (152)

Israel as a Settler Colonial State

If we want to analyse the efficacy of violence in the armed resistance movement by the Palestinians, we first need to settle the debate, whether Israel is a colonial or settler colonial state? The debate around this topic is fierce, especially after the October 7th incident. There are two sides of this debate, the first side is with the motion and the other is against the motion. The Israeli or sympathisers of Israel leave no stone unturned to prove how Israel does not fit in the definition of colonial state. Like Alan Dowty who is Professor Emeritus of Political Science at the University of Notre Dame explains in his article "Is Israel a settler colonial state?". Dowty uses bookish definitions of colonialism and makes desperate attempts to fit it with the formation of Israel and how when the Jews reached the shores of Palestine, they were nothing more than refugees. His attempt seems like a child who is trying hard to make a piece of puzzle fit in a wrong place to complete the puzzle.

We need to be aware of the fact that the colonisation of Israel cannot just be measured by using bookish definitions, rather what Israel is really doing on the ground. The grassroots realities differ hugely from the bookish facts that Prof. Dowty is taking up in his article. Haleema Shah in her article "Is Israel a "settler-colonial" state? The debate, explained."

published on Vox website, again takes up the question “Is Israel a colonial state?” She historically studies the Israel’s atrocities in the area and also looks at the consequences of British colonialism. “While under British control, Palestine saw violent clashes between Zionists and Arabs, and its demography changed rapidly, with the Jewish population increasing from 6 percent to 33 percent. In the eyes of Arab nationalists, the argument was a simple one: A foreign power took control of Arab land and promised it to another foreign group.” (Shah)

Giving examples of China and India, Shah argues that settler colonialism is not a western thing. China is incentivising the Han migration to Tibet and India in his constant efforts to change the demographics of Kashmir. Shah writes, “Israel’s continued occupation of Palestinian territories motivates charges of present-day colonialism.” (Shah) After considering both arguments, it can be concluded that Israel’s ongoing occupation on the Palestinian land is not justifiable through the bookish definitions of colonialism. When ground realities are starkly different from the idealised version of Israel's existence and with proper proof of Israel misdoings in the reason. It can easily be concluded that Israel is a settler colonial state.

Violence in the Context of Armed Struggle in Palestine and Israel Conflict

This part of the essay will talk about the resistance movement of the Palestinians and its efficacy. To reach a conclusion, the study uses ideas from both of the theorists Fanon and Arendt. As discussed previously in the essay, Fanon is a supporter of violence in the armed struggles of colonised people against colonialism whereas Arendt opposes the idea, saying that violence cannot create power. She is of the opinion that violence furthers even more violence. It may prove effective in achieving short term goal, but in the long run violence is always a bad idea.

Palestinian resistance has used violence as a means of fighting against the occupiers, to list a few the coastal road attack (1978), the first *intifada* (1987), the second *intifada* (2000), the Passover massacre. These are to name a few prominent one apart from this various resistance groups including Hamas has been attacking through rockets and missiles. The latest one could be the October 7th attacks. (Council on Foreign Relations) These violent clashes and attacks have been resulted in huge number of casualties. In the first *intifada*, it is reported that around hundred Israelis and a thousand Palestinians died. (Hawaleshka) The number of Palestinian people is tenfold that of the Israeli. The Passover massacre in which a Palestinian suicide bomber slipped through security in a hotel and set off a powerful explosion. This bombing reportedly killed 19 Israelis and at least 100 were injured. (Hockstader)

In more recent years, Hamas and Hezbollah including other minor resistance groups are

targeting Israel through various channels, often few but casualties arise from these attacks as well. Considering the October 7th attacks, Center for Strategic & International Studies, which considers the attacks as a terrorist attacks, report 1200 fatalities in the attack. (Byman et al.) There's little doubt that violence has affected people from both sides, Palestinians and Israelis have taken blows of violence, but the signs of mass destruction are visible more conspicuously among the Palestinians.

Studying these violent actions through the lense of the two theorists in question, the conclusion that comes out is that even though Fanon never endorses violence he admits its necessity to bring about the self-respect and consciousness of the oppressed people. Fanon writes "At the level of individuals, violence is a cleansing force. It frees the native from his inferiority complex and from his despair and inaction; it makes him fearless and restores his self-respect." (94) So one can conclude that even though the violence might not be immediately helpful for the Palestinians to regain control over their land from the colonialists but it, according to Fanon, surely restores their self-respect and confidence.

Hannah Arendt's main contention regarding violence is that violence may be able to destroy power, but it cannot hold it. (155) In the context of Israel and Palestine, we can observe that the state of Israel has been holding power through the means of violence since 1947. Her theory struggles to hold ground here and as rightly pointed out by Chad Kautzer in his essay, Arendt's concerns are only limited to the violence inflicted by the revolutionaries and resistance fighter while she comfortably leaves the state inflicted violence aside. (2)

Countering another point raised by Hannah Arendt where she opposes violence saying it cannot be used to gain long-lasting results and the achievements are often short-lived while the price is too high. (152) In the context of Palestinians, they have two options either remain silent and face violence from the "the individual perspective" (Wyrick 107) or fight back and face violence that way. Fanon sides with the latter, he says that it is the coloniser who enables the native to use violence. When continuously facing the oppression inflicted by the Israelis, the Palestinians would always be mindful of their position and with an anger within them. "The symbols of social order--the police, the bugle calls in the barracks, military parades and the waving flags--are at one and the same time inhibitory and stimulating: for they do not convey the message "Don't dare to budge"; rather, they cry out "Get ready to attack."" (Fanon 53)

Conclusion

While it is a consensus among the masses that violence is a noble idea, however there are certain situations where people are forced to resort to violence, and according to Fanon decolonisation is such a situation which cannot operation without the help of violence. (35) The Palestine question cannot thus be solved without the help of violence because on the

other side of the field is a state which has support of the superpower of the world. The ideals of non-violence as pinned down by MK Gandhi and Martin Luther King are also useless in this situation because the opposite team is not a waning empire broken down by two consecutive world wars. Surprisingly, Hannah Arendt also subscribes to this view that non-violent movements will not turn out that good in front of ruthless forces. "In a head-on clash between violence and power, the outcome is hardly in doubt. If Gandhi's enormously powerful and successful strategy of non-violent resistance had met with a different enemy – Stalin's Russia, Hitler's Germany, even pre-war Japan, instead of England—the outcome would not have been decolonisation, but massacre and submission." (152)

Likewise, in the context of Palestine and Israel, one cannot say that Palestinians have a slight chance in front of Israel. The Zionist aspirations will not take long to regain control on whatever bits and pieces of land that the Palestinians are currently holding. Talking of land Fanon also emphasises on the importance of land in the process of colonisation and subsequently decolonisation. "For a colonized people the most essential value, because the most concrete, is first and foremost the land: the land which will bring them bread and, above all, dignity." (44) For Palestinians, Land is everything, in an article published in Al-Jazeera by Mohammed Hussein and Mohammad Haddad titled "How Israel destroyed Gaza's ability to feed itself", the authors analyse the destruction of crops and farmlands during the war. "During one short pause in fighting from November 22 to December 1, Palestinian farmers ran to harvest their olives and extract oil, because they do not know any other way to live, and because they needed the harvest." (Haddad and Hussein)

In conclusion, violence in the context of Palestine and Israel is an important part as it is a way of Palestinians to fight back the giant who is taking over their land and killing their people. Non-violent means as suggested by Hannah Arendt do not work in these circumstances and Fanon's idea prevails. Analysing the process of decolonisation, Fanon comes correct about the process that it is inherently violent. Even though it is not bringing any immediate results for the Palestinian people, it is comparatively better than sitting stagnant and watching your land being snatched away from you.

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